

FELSIC LAVAS OF THE ARGENTINE ISLANDS FORMATION (WILHELM ARCHIPELAGO, WEST ANTARCTICA)

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The Argentine Islands, where the Ukrainian Antarctic Station is located, are composed mainly of volcanic rocks. They belong to the Upper Jurassic Volcanic Group or the Argentine Islands Formation of the Jurassic-Cretaceous age. D. Elliot identified the following petrographic varieties among volcanites: trachytic andesites, porphyritic andesites, dacite crystal tuffs, and dacite breccias. As can be seen from the division, no lavas of felsic composition have been recognized among the rock representatives until recently. The first outcrops of felsic lava were found by Oleksandr Mytrokhyn in 2017 and 2019 on the Corner Islands. He provisionally described them as dacite crystal tuffs. These rocks form most of the East Corner Island as well as adjacent hill on the West Corner Island. Their prominent feature is fluidal structures which can be seen in outcrops due to the alternation of 0,5–50 cm bands differing in color shade and resistance to weathering. Fluidal textures dip at an angle 25–60° on the south-east or south-west.

A detailed laboratory study of the collected sample was started by Anna Mashyrova. Microscopic examinations revealed the presence of felsic effusive rocks and not just crystal tuffs among the studied samples. The main evidences for their lava origin are petrographic features. First, in thin sections, they clearly demonstrate a typical fluidal microstructure in the matrix, which is evidence of lava flow. Moreover, the orientation of some plagioclase phenocrysts aligns with the flow direction. Second, phenocrysts represented by plagioclase and quartz are usually idiomorphic. That is, they are not characterized by clastic forms as in tuffs. Third, lithoclasts are either completely absent in these rocks or their number does not exceed a few units.

Common petrographic features of the felsic effusive rocks include porphyritic texture, felsitic to spherulitic matrix, complete devitrification of volcanic glass, and low-temperature hydrothermal mineralization (albite, epidote, chlorite, sericite, and pyrite). The primary preserved minerals are quartz and partly plagioclase, as well as some accessories (apatite, zircon, allanite, ilmenite). Therefore, the degree of rock preservation can be considered moderate.

The discovery of felsic effusive rocks provides a basis for determining the center of a volcanic eruption, which should be located near the distribution area of viscous dacitic and rhyolitic lavas. In addition, lavas are generally best suited for geochemical modeling of magmatic processes. Finally, since isotopic dating of volcanic rocks from the Argentine Islands Formation is absent, and previous studies by Anna Mashyrova did not find a reliable mineral-chronometer in andesite lavas, the discovery of zircons and allanite in felsic lavas has become equally significant. Importantly, the zircons have euhedral shapes and sizes suitable for isotopic dating.